

Advancing smart building upgrades through an innovative decision support framework for smart readiness indicator implementation: A Greek case study

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ABSTRACT

The European Union's Energy Performance of Buildings Directive, which serves as a basis for developing energy efficiency and sustainability in the building industry, introduced the Smart Readiness Indicator to evaluate the digital and intelligent capabilities of buildings. Current tools predominantly focus on offering standardized Smart Readiness Indicator assessments, often lacking mechanisms that offer guidance on actionable improvements. The proposed novel decision support framework enhances this traditional evaluation methodology by linking smartness assessments with personalized upgrade recommendations. It suggests individualized market-based solutions for commercial technologies and ranks them using a multi-perspective approach, enabling building stakeholders to obtain a comprehensive estimate of the overall upgrade cost. A case study of a non-residential office building in Athens, Greece, demonstrates the potential for significant improvements in energy performance and occupant comfort through targeted smart readiness upgrades. The optimal solutions for all three ranking metrics are presented, highlighting the differences in each of the distinct approaches. Results indicate that integrating advanced systems, such as thermostats, energy monitoring tools, and heating solutions, enhances both Smart Readiness Indicator scores and financial efficiency. This research underscores the transformative role of smart buildings in achieving the European Union's climate neutrality goals by 2050. While challenges such as upfront costs, regional variability and subjectivity of the assessment remain, the findings argue for continuous improvement of the methodology to address the different needs and energy requirements of buildings. Integrating the Smart Readiness Indicator into broader energy and climate strategies is a critical step towards sustainable urban development.

1. Introduction

The European Union (EU) has set ambitious climate and energy targets in alignment with the European Green Deal and the European Climate Law [1], committing to a 55 % reduction in Greenhouse Gas (GHG) emissions by 2030 and reaching climate neutrality by 2050. The building sector lies at the heart of this transition, as it accounts for approximately 40 % of total energy consumption and 36 % of overall greenhouse gas emissions in the EU [2]. Given that nearly 75 % of the EU's building stock is outdated and remains largely unrenovated, energy inefficiency remains a major challenge [3]. Current renovation rates

remain low, with only 1 % of buildings renovated annually, and deep renovations occurring at an even lower rate of 0.2 % [4].

A key component of the EU's energy transition strategy is the smartification of buildings, which involves the integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT)-enabled solutions to optimize energy performance, enhance occupant comfort, and support energy grid stability [5,6]. Smart buildings are equipped with digital technologies such as automated control systems, smart meters, and demand-response mechanisms, to interact dynamically with the energy grid and adapt in real time to occupant needs, electricity prices, and environmental conditions [7].

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To support the digital transformation of the built environment, the European Commission (EC) introduced the Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI) in the 2018 revision of the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) (Directive 2018/844/EU) [8]. The 2024 revision (EU/2024/1275) strengthened the directive's emphasis on smart technologies, requiring the adoption of smart meters, Building Management Systems (BMS), and digital automation tools to improve energy efficiency and facilitate integration with renewable energy sources [9].

The SRI provides a standardized methodology for assessing how effectively a building can integrate smart technologies to optimize energy efficiency and occupant comfort [8]. The methodology for calculating the SRI was formalized through a Delegated Regulation (2020/2155) [10] and an Implementing Regulation (2020/2156) [11], which established guidelines for its application by EU Member States. The EC also conducted technical studies to develop a comprehensive framework, identifying key "smart ready services" that define a building's smart readiness potential [7].

Despite the structured approach of the SRI framework, its implementation remains in an early stage across the EU, with only a few Member States actively piloting or testing the methodology [12]. The availability of automated and user-friendly SRI calculation tools has improved accessibility, enabling building owners, policymakers, and stakeholders to evaluate the smart readiness of buildings efficiently, although a critical gap persists in the practical application of the SRI. Existing tools [13] focus primarily on the assessment phase—calculating a building's smart readiness level based on the presence and performance of predefined smart services [14–17]. However, they lack methodologies that translate these assessments into actionable market-based strategies for technological upgrades tailored to a building's context. In particular, there is a profound lack of frameworks that highlight key technical domains for improvement and assess the impact of specific upgrades on these domains. Most SRI assessment models emphasize evaluating the presence of installed smart technologies rather than providing a structured and holistic approach for identifying and prioritizing cost-effective upgrade pathways. This absence of upgrade-focused methodologies presents a major barrier to scaling up the deployment of Smart Ready Technologies (SRTs), as building owners lack clear guidance on the technical and economic feasibility of implementing smart energy solutions.

In this context, this paper aims to bridge the gap between the SRI assessment and actionable smart building upgrades by introducing a methodological framework that investigates the potential for targeted SRI-driven upgrades in buildings across the EU. This framework advances the SRI methodology by integrating a decision support layer that goes beyond static evaluation, supporting building owners, occupants, policymakers, etc. in making informed decisions regarding smart building transformations. To achieve this, tailored market-based smartness upgrade scenarios comprising different commercial SRT spanning across all involved technical domains, are taken into account, with particular focus on their economic implications. This added dimension transforms the SRI from a diagnostic tool into an actionable guide for planning, prioritizing, and investing in smart building enhancements. Moreover, the analysis offers key insights into the optimal upgrade pathways in terms of SRI improvement, total investment cost, and cost effectiveness. By addressing the lack of structured frameworks and digital tools needed for effective SRI-driven building upgrades, this study contributes to the broader discourse on smart building readiness, energy efficiency, and the digital transformation of the EU building sector. The findings are expected to support evidence-based policy recommendations and guide relevant stakeholders toward accelerating the transition to smart, sustainable, and climate-resilient buildings.

The remaining part of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 provides an extended literature review, summarizing previous research on smart buildings and the SRI framework, while outlining the existing knowledge gap. Section 3 details the methodological framework, explaining the SRI calculation methodology and the upgrade assessment

methodology used to evaluate potential building enhancements. Section 4 presents a case study, demonstrating the practical application of the proposed upgrade methodology. Section 5 analyzes the results of the case study, evaluating the impact of different upgrade scenarios on achieving targeted SRI scores. Section 6 discusses the broader implications of the findings, considering economic feasibility, policy alignment, and future research directions. Finally, Section 7 concludes the study, summarizing key insights and suggesting pathways for the enhanced adoption of smart technologies in the EU building sector.

2. Literature review

The SRI methodology is gaining traction in literature, with several studies exploring its applications, limitations, and potential improvements across various building types and climates. However, the body of research remains limited, highlighting the need for further exploration.

Volkov and Batov [18] emphasized the critical role of input data in determining the effectiveness of SRI assessments. Their sensitivity analysis on a university campus in Odense, Denmark, showcased how variations in the number of considered services and the weighting systems impacted the overall assessment. Horák and Kabele [14] investigated the applicability of the SRI across various building types in the Czech Republic, highlighting both its strengths and limitations. Janhunen et al. [15] assessed the applicability of the SRI in Northern Europe, particularly in cold climates where heating is the dominant energy consumption factor. Their findings indicated that the SRI's system-oriented approach did not effectively differentiate the unique features of cold-climate buildings, especially those with advanced district heating systems. They also pinpointed subjectivity concerns in the methodology, which could create a niche for score manipulation. A follow-up study by Janhunen et al. [19] further examined the economic viability of smart energy system investments using SRI metrics, revealing that its direct correlation with monetized energy savings remains unclear.

Markoska et al. [20] suggested an automated approach for the SRI calculation, utilizing metadata models in a Performance Testing (PTing) framework. They demonstrated that evaluating buildings' smartness solutions typically requires considerable manual analysis. Al Dakheel et al. [21] explored various definitions of smartness in the literature to develop a comprehensive understanding of smart buildings. Following an extensive analysis of reports, legislation, and research papers, they proposed 36 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and classified them based on their smartness features, laying the groundwork for future assessments of building intelligence. Fokaides et al. [16] investigated the impact of the SRI on building energy performance through a case study of an educational building, which achieved an SRI score of 52%. They concluded that the SRI methodology necessitates integration with other energy efficiency assessment frameworks, to better cater to specific building types. Vigna et al. [22] applied the SRI methodology to a nearly zero-energy office building, conducting parallel evaluations with two expert groups. They emphasized the importance of collecting precise data that directly affects building service functionality and argued that smartness should enhance energy efficiency and adapt building operations to occupant needs and grid demands.

Märzinger and Österreicher [23] extended the SRI's scope by delivering a set of equations applicable at the district level, enabling a quantitative assessment of load-shifting potential in smart buildings. Ramezani et al. [17] tackled challenges related to implementing the SRI methodology in the Mediterranean climate, specifically in Portugal. Their evaluation of two case buildings revealed that, while the SRI framework was suitable for the region, it did not fully account for the impact of all energy efficiency measures and Indoor Environment Quality (IEQ) improvements. Becchio et al. [24] focused on applying the SRI in an energy center in Turin, Italy. Their research assessed several retrofitting scenarios related to energy management and control, analyzing their impact on the SRI score of the building. Their findings

confirmed that the SRI methodology effectively evaluated the energy center's smart readiness but also unveiled inherent challenges within the framework. Martínez et al. [25] explored the SRI's application in a university building in Zaragoza, Spain, investigating the potential of integrating Internet of Things (IoT) devices as a means to enhance building performance and meet Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Their findings underscored the role of SRI in evaluating the effectiveness of smart building technologies. Canale et al. [26] applied the SRI in residential buildings across three scenarios, emphasizing that a smart energy retrofit achieved an SRI score of 27.5 %, compared to 15.7 % for a simple energy retrofit.

Apostolopoulos et al. [27,27] evaluated the SRI methodology for residential buildings across different renovation scenarios, finding that relatively low expenditures are required to increase the smartness of buildings constructed after the EPBD implementation compared to older buildings. Plienaitis et al. [28] focused on the applicability of the SRI in educational buildings located in Lithuania, assessing the impact of modernizing the heating system and integrating advanced engineering technologies, on the SRI score. In their findings, the authors noted that by upgrading the heating system and implementing cutting-edge technologies, the SRI score could potentially rise by 41 %. Avendano et al. [29] introduced a framework to assess the smart readiness of highly electrified buildings, aiming to enhance existing systems and establish minimum criteria for future constructions. They applied the SRI and the Smart by Powerhouse scheme to ten diverse non-residential buildings in Norway, with a particular focus on quantifying energy flexibility, especially in relation to electric vehicle charging (EVC). Their findings indicated smart readiness levels ranging from 21.6 % to 31.7 %, highlighting the importance of distinguishing between current Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning (HVAC) technologies for accurate assessments. Tak et al. [30] presented a framework to analyze drivers and barriers to smart home technology adoption, validated through a survey on HVAC systems, highlighting the role of trust, privacy, transparency, and user interaction in shaping adoption intent. Studies by Li et al. [31], Märzinger and Österreicher [32], Koltios et al. [33], and Seduikyte et al. [34] emphasized the importance of further developing Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) to incorporate the SRI, arguing that this could motivate investments in smart technologies and energy savings.

Bleil De Souza et al. [35] introduced OntoAgency, an agency-based design ontology that maps stakeholder relationships in smart building operations, integrating Actor-Network Theory (ANT) to bridge social and technical knowledge and address data security concerns. Samaras et al. [36] evaluated the readiness of European countries to adopt the SRI using a multicriteria framework that integrated social, political, economic, and technological dimensions through the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) and TOPSIS methodology. Arsenopoulos et al. [37] explored the customization of the SRI methodological framework by adjusting domain weighting factors using the "energy balance" method, demonstrating how tailored assessments—applied to a typical Greek single-family house—can yield more accurate results compared to the standard methodology, particularly in energy efficiency and occupant comfort. Qaisar et al. [38] evaluated real-world multi-zone Occupancy-Centric Control (OCC) systems, analyzing HVAC operational intervals and demonstrating how customized control strategies enhance energy efficiency and occupant comfort in dynamic and stable building environments.

Agboola & Nnezi [39] explored the synergies between smart technology and human thermal comfort. Their findings support the notion that occupant-centric upgrades enhance livability, which this paper expands by offering actionable, cost-effective SRI-based interventions. Another recent study by Michailidis et al. [40] highlighted that even low-complexity smart technologies, such as minimal-IoT solutions, can significantly enhance building performance. Similarly, Danassis et al. [41] showed that smart thermostats applied to legacy HVAC systems also demonstrated notable improvements in efficiency and control.

These approaches enable functional upgrades with minimal infrastructure disruption, offering scalable, cost-effective interventions, which is aligned with the goal of this study. Korkas et al. [42] presented a simulation-based optimization approach for designing an energy management system in grid-connected, solar-equipped microgrids with heterogeneous occupancy schedules, aiming to minimize energy costs and maximize occupant thermal comfort by intelligently adapting energy demand based on occupancy patterns. In a follow-up study, Korkas et al. [43] proposed a novel two-level control algorithm for demand response in renewable-powered microgrids, optimizing both energy cost and occupant thermal comfort through decentralized and centralized feedback, and demonstrated its scalability and robustness across varying conditions. Such approaches complement this study's objective of promoting scalable smart readiness improvements, especially in existing buildings with limited system flexibility.

Building on previous research, most existing studies primarily focus on technical assessments and performance metrics, emphasizing gaps and challenges in the SRI application. Nevertheless, they fail to provide a systematic framework for extracting tailored solutions for the users towards implementing smartness upgrades that consider also financial implications. This paper addresses this critical gap by presenting a holistic methodology that accompanies SRI evaluations with a comprehensive set of market-based smartness upgrade solutions, supported by economic analysis. By doing so, it offers a well-rounded perspective on how different upgrade scenarios are able to enhance the smart readiness of a building while aligning with budgetary constraints and financial goals.

3. Methodological framework

The proposed methodological framework is designed to exploit the results of the SRI assessment framework's application, laying out targeted tailored combinations of market-based solutions structured in scenarios, enabling EU building owners and tenants to make informed decisions on smart upgrades. As of this, the methodology consists of two interconnected layers applied in discrete steps. The first layer is linked to the well-established SRI assessment methodology, as proposed by the related EU report [7], and will be used as a sub-component of the introduced methodology, briefly described in Section 3.1, for clarity and inclusiveness reasons. The second layer rolls out the introduced methodology and acts as the focal point of this study, developed to propose building-adjusted commercial upgrade solutions. The respective steps of these two distinct although interconnected parts of the framework are exhibited in Fig. 1.

3.1. SRI assessment methodology

The SRI calculation methodology evaluates a building's smart readiness by assessing 54 smart services across nine technical domains: 1) Heating, 2) Domestic hot water (DHW), 3) Cooling, 4) Ventilation, 5) Lighting, 6) Dynamic building envelope, 7) Electricity, 8) Electric vehicle charging, and 9) Monitoring & control. These services are scored on a functionality scale indicating their smartness level, from 0 (non-intelligent) to 4 (highly advanced) based on their complexity and features, against seven impact criteria. These functionality levels are pre-defined for each of the 54 smart services via a service catalogue, as established by the EU technical SRI report [7] and are based on criteria such as the degree of automation, responsiveness, interoperability, and capacity to support energy flexibility. These criteria are further clustered into three key functionalities that highlight the main objectives of the SRI. The interconnection of the impact criteria and key functionalities is shown in Table 1, along with the related technical domains [7].

The SRI assessment methodology [7] corresponds to the first module of the proposed framework comprising ten steps (steps 1–10 in Fig. 1). To specify, step 1 begins with gathering basic building details mainly focusing on the building's type (residential/non-residential) and

Fig. 1. SRI upgrade decision support framework.

Table 1
Overview of technical domains, impact criteria and key functionalities included in the SRI methodology.

Technical domain		
1. Heating	2. Cooling	3. Domestic hot water
4. Ventilation	5. Lighting	6. Dynamic building envelope
7. Electricity	8. Electric vehicle charging	9. Monitoring & control
Impact criterion		
1. Energy efficiency		Key functionality
2. Maintenance & fault protection		1. Energy performance & operation
3. Comfort		2. Response to the needs of occupants
4. Convenience		
5. Health, well-being & accessibility		
6. Information to occupants		
7. Energy flexibility & storage		3. Energy flexibility

location (North Europe/West Europe/South Europe/North-East Europe/South-East Europe), to be used for the selection of the domain weighting factors, defaulting to EU guidelines or manually set per se. Step 2 is related to the selection of the SRI assessment method: Method A (27 services, for existing residential and small non-residential buildings), Method B (54 services, for new residential and large non-residential buildings), or Method C (residential and non-residential buildings with installed sensors and smart meters). Step 3 includes the identification of present, absent but mandatory (e.g., due to national regulation) or absent and not mandatory technical domains. Based on these selections, a customized list of technical domains is formulated, focusing on their included smart-ready services. In step 4, the relevant services within each technical domain are identified via a triage process, in order to be assessed for the specific building. In case some services are deemed non-relevant, not applicable, or unnecessary, the total SRI score is calculated as a percentage of the actual building score over the maximum attainable score of the building. Regarding step 5, services are rated on a five-tier scale ranging between 0 and 4, with higher levels indicating higher impact to a building's smartness. In general, these ratings are determined by an authorized assessor, responsible for carrying out the SRI assessment in a building. There are three discrete approaches to elicit the weighting factors of the methodology components: Fixed weighting which implies fixed weighting values based on the established SRI methodology [7], Equal weighting (equally weights among all technical domains) or Energy balance weighting (hybrid; energy-based weights). Step 6 involves the selection of the weighting factors for the key functionalities and impact criteria. For the key functionalities and impact criteria weights, the "equal weighting" method is suggested, while for the weighting of technical domains against the involved impact criteria, a mix of fixed, equal, and energy balance methods are applied jointly (step 7). Next, in step 8 service scores are aggregated at the domain level against each impact criterion. The aggregation of service scores follows again the equal weighting approach. A total score is then calculated in step 9 at key functionality level as a weighted sum of all impact criteria scores (equal weighting approach). Finally in step 10, the total SRI score is derived by summing the three weighted key functionality scores, classifying buildings into seven smart readiness categories (<20 % to 90–100 %) [7].

3.2. SRI decision support framework

The SRI Decision Support Framework (DSF) constitutes the second module of the suggested context, where the methodological parameters have to be defined (steps 11–18 in Fig. 1). It implements a rigorous, systematic methodology designed to evaluate and prioritize technological interventions aimed at enhancing a building's smart readiness capabilities. This structured approach integrates both quantitative assessments and qualitative evaluations to ensure that decisions are based on established scientific principles and robust data.

The process initiates with the definition of an SRI target, representing the desired level of smart functionality that should be met for the

building under evaluation. This target is established by benchmarking against the building's existing SRI score, as calculated through the standardized SRI assessment framework. The target functions as a quantitative threshold against which all potential intervention scenarios are evaluated, thereby facilitating a comparative analysis of upgrade alternatives. The selection of the upgrade scenarios is informed by a curated database of commercially available technologies, systems, or products, called Intervention Technologies (ITs). These technologies are characterized by their potential to upgrade specific smart ready services, when integrated into the building, covering all nine technical domains. A systematic mapping process is then employed to link each IT to the corresponding smart ready services it influences. Given the multifaceted nature of these technologies, a single IT may affect multiple services. Furthermore, for each affected service, the maximum achievable functionality level is determined, providing a baseline for subsequent impact analysis. The mapping of the ITs to the specific SRI services and respective functionality levels is carried out manually using expert knowledge and then cross-validated using market research.

Following the mapping of ITs to smart ready services, the framework identifies the intersection of applicable services in the building under evaluation and those impacted by the identified ITs. This intersection analysis is critical for isolating the applicable services and their associated ITs that will be subjected to further examination for potential enhancements in smart readiness.

A decision node is then introduced to assess whether at least one of the building's applicable services is influenced by the identified ITs, based on the mapping outcomes. If no services are impacted, the framework concludes that no viable upgrades are possible. Conversely, if more than one service is affected, the framework isolates the corresponding ITs and proceeds with a quantitative evaluation of their potential impacts.

The next phase involves comparing the new maximum functionality levels of these services—achievable through IT installation—with their current performance baselines. If the proposed interventions do not yield performance improvement, the corresponding services and ITs are systematically excluded from further analysis. However, in case an improvement is identified, the methodology calculates the expected benefits of the upgrades for both standalone ITs and IT combinations. This step incorporates multi-scenario modeling to ensure that all potential configurations are considered, thereby enhancing the robustness of the decision-making process.

The gain at the SRI level for each scenario is quantified by applying the equations, structured in intermediate steps to ease understanding and readability:

Intermediate Step 1: Calculation of the gained impact scores of the selected services.

First, the impact score of each selected service within the present technical domains across the involved impact criteria is measured:

$$I_s = I_{ic}(FL_{s,d}) \quad (1)$$

where:

- s stands for the selected service,
- ic stands for the impact criterion,
- d stands for the technical domain,
- $FL_{s,d}$ is the functionality level of selected service s in technical domain d ,
- $I_{ic}(FL_{s,d})$ is the score of selected service s in technical domain d for impact criterion ic , according to the service's functionality level.

Then, the gained impact score of each selected service is calculated by the mathematical expression below:

$$I_s^{gain} = I_{ic}^{new}(FL_{s,d}) - I_{ic}^{ex}(FL_{s,d}) \quad (2)$$

where:

- $I_{ic}^{new}(FL_{s,d})$ is the score of selected service s in technical domain d for impact criterion ic for the new functionality level,
- $I_{ic}^{ex}(FL_{s,d})$ is the score of selected service s in technical domain d for impact criterion ic for the existing functionality level.

Intermediate Step 2: Calculation of the aggregated impact scores of the selected services included in each technical domain.

The impact scores of the selected services are aggregated at technical domain level against each impact criterion, as follows:

$$I_{d,ic} = \sum_{i=1}^{N_d} I_s \quad (3)$$

where:

- N_d is the total number of selected services in technical domain d .

Next, the maximum sum of impact scores of the selected services at technical domain level against each impact criterion is measured:

$$I_{d,ic}^{max} = \sum_{i=1}^{N_d} I_s^{max} \quad (4)$$

where:

- N_d is the total number of i) selected services and ii) non-selected but mandatory services in technical domain d ,
- I_s^{max} is the maximum score of service s in technical domain d for impact criterion ic , according to the service's maximum functionality level.

Intermediate Step 3: Calculation of the gained smart readiness scores of the impact criteria and technical domains.

The gained smart readiness score of each impact criterion is computed by the following formula:

$$SR_{ic}^{gain} = \frac{\sum_{d=1}^N w_{d,ic} \cdot (I_{d,ic}^{new} - I_{d,ic}^{ex})}{\sum_{d=1}^N w_{d,ic} \cdot I_{d,ic}^{max}} \cdot 100 \quad (5)$$

where:

- N is the total number of technical domains,
- $w_{d,ic}$ is the weight of the technical domain d for impact criterion ic (domain weighing),
- $I_{d,ic}^{new}$ is the score of the impact criterion ic in technical domain d for the new functionality level,
- $I_{d,ic}^{ex}$ is the score of the impact criterion ic in technical domain d for the existing functionality level,

The gained smart readiness score of each technical domain is calculated by the equation below:

$$SR_d^{gain} = \sum_{ic=1}^M w_{ic} \cdot \frac{I_{d,ic}^{new} - I_{d,ic}^{ex}}{I_{d,ic}^{max}} \cdot 100 \quad (6)$$

where:

- M is the total number of impact criteria,
- w_{ic} is the weight of impact criterion ic (impact weighting).

Intermediate Step 4: Calculation of the gained smart readiness scores of the key functionalities.

The gained smart readiness score of each key functionality is calculated as follows:

$$SR_f^{gain} = \sum_{ic=1}^M w_{f,ic} \cdot SR_{ic}^{gain} \quad (7)$$

where:

- $w_{f,ic}$ is the weight of impact criterion ic in relation to its key functionality f .

Intermediate Step 5: Calculation of the gained SRI score.

The gained SRI score is the weighted sum of the three functionality level scores:

$$SRI_{gain} = \sum_{f=1}^P w_f \cdot SR_f^{gain} \quad (8)$$

where:

- P is the total number of key functionalities,
- w_f is the weight of key functionality f .

Upon quantifying the SRI gain, the framework evaluates whether the proposed interventions in each scenario meet the predefined SRI target. If none of the scenarios satisfy this criterion, the process concludes with no feasible IT upgrades. On the contrary, if one or more scenarios meet the target, they are compiled into a list of potential upgrade pathways for further comparative evaluation.

The final phase involves the ranking of these scenarios based on multiple criteria to support informed decision-making. The scenarios are assessed according to three primary indicators: 1) total cost, reflecting the estimated financial expenditure associated with each intervention, including capital and operational expenditures; 2) SRI gain, representing the level of improvement in smart readiness, derived from the difference between the baseline and post-intervention SRI scores; and 3) cost effectiveness, which balances the scales between investment and performance and is computed as the ratio of total investment cost to the SRI score gained from the intervention (€/SRI gain). Essentially, this indicator has been designed to express the amount of money needed to be invested by the user, in order to increase the SRI score of a building by one unit. The DSF enables this multi-objective scenario comparison by explicitly presenting trade-offs between SRI gain, total investment cost, and cost effectiveness. Each of these criteria reflects a distinct stakeholder priority: technical performance, financial feasibility, or investment return. It should be clarified that the framework does not assume a single optimal solution but rather presents alternative ranked scenarios to accommodate different objectives. For instance, a solution that yields maximum SRI improvement might involve significantly higher costs compared to another that delivers modest gains more economically. To support navigating these trade-offs, the DSF allows users to prioritize or filter scenarios based on their needs or constraints.

To address the complexity inherent in the upgrade selection process, the DSF employs a controlled combinatorial enumeration of upgrade scenarios, evaluating combinations of 1 to k technologies, assessing each

in terms of SRI gain, total cost, and cost effectiveness. In addition, only technology upgrades that achieve a minimum SRI gain threshold are considered for combinations, while candidate scenarios are subsequently prioritized based on the three ranking metrics, enabling early identification of the highest-performing solutions without requiring an exhaustive search. This approach ensures computational efficiency, with all evaluations completed within seconds on standard computing hardware, thereby facilitating seamless integration with user-facing digital applications.

Through this structured, scientifically grounded methodology, the SRI DSF provides a robust framework for the selection and prioritization of ITs. This ensures that decisions are not only technically robust but also economically sustainable, thereby supporting the broader objective of advancing smart building technologies in alignment with energy efficiency goals and sustainability mandates.

4. Case study

The case study was conducted to evaluate the SRI upgrade methodology, described in Section 3, utilizing the IT concept. Based on the current SRI score of the building under evaluation (extracted from the SRI assessment) and the assigned target SRI score, the building retrofit methodology (developed by the DSF) provides a list of upgrade scenarios

with specific commercial products and building systems, ranked by one of the three available criteria, as defined in Section 3.2. The key aspect of the case study is to examine the added value of the SRI upgrade concept and verify the usability of the developed tool in a real-life scenario.

The investigated concept of the study was applied to a non-residential office building of one of the largest companies in Greece, located in the city of Athens. The building belongs to the climate zone of South Europe, was constructed in 2007 (original state) and has a net floor area of 3830.39 m². The key characteristics of the building are presented in Table 2, while the applicable smart ready services with their respective functionality levels are shown in Table 3. The assignment of functionality levels to each applicable service was based on an on-site audit and a detailed review of the building's technical systems and control capabilities, conducted by a certified assessor.

It should be noted that access to the necessary information and the SRI assessment results of the case study building were provided through the EU's LIFE project SRI-ENACT [44] (Grant agreement No. 101077201), which aims to engage stakeholders in national and EU level to co-create tools and services for the SRI uptake. As part of this project, all data collection and processing activities strictly adhered to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) to ensure the confidentiality and protection of sensitive information. Anonymization measures were rigorously applied, including the removal of any

Table 2
Key characteristics of case study building.

Location	Climate zone	Building type	Building usage	Floor area (m ²)	Construction year	Building state
Athens, Greece	South Europe	Non-residential	Office	3830.39	2007	Original

Table 3
Applicable smart ready services and functionality levels of case study building.

Technical domain	Smart ready service	Functionality level
Heating	H-1a. Heat emission control	Level 1: Central automatic control (e.g. central thermostat) – 50 % Level 2: Individual room control (e.g. thermostatic valves, or electronic controller) – 50 % Level 0: No automatic control
	H-1c. Control of distribution fluid temperature (supply or return air flow or water flow) – Similar function can be applied to the control of direct electric heating networks	Level 2: Multi-Stage control Level 0: Constant temperature control
	H-1d. Control of distribution pumps in networks	Level 1: Central or remote reporting of current performance KPIs (e.g. temperatures, submetering energy usage) Level 0: Automatic control on/off
	H-2a. Heat generator control (all except heat pumps)	
	H-3. Report information regarding domestic hot water performance	
Domestic hot water	DHW-1a. Control of DHW storage charging (with direct electric heating or integrated electric heat pump)	
Cooling	C-1a. Cooling emission control	Level 1: Central automatic control – 50 % Level 2: Individual room control – 50 % Level 0: Constant temperature control
	C-1c. Control of distribution network chilled water temperature (supply or return)	Level 2: Total interlock (control system ensures no simultaneous heating and cooling can take place) Level 1: Multi-stage control of cooling production capacity depending on the load or demand (e.g. on/off of several compressors)
	C-1f. Interlock avoiding simultaneous heating and cooling in the same room	Level 1: Fixed sequencing based on loads only: e.g. depending on the generators characteristics such as absorption chiller vs. centrifugal chiller
	C-2a. Generator control for cooling	Level 1: Central or remote reporting of current performance KPIs (e.g. temperatures, submetering energy usage) Level 0: No ventilation system or manual control – 50 %
	C-2b. Sequencing for different cooling operators	Level 1: Clock control – 50 % Level 0: Manual on/off switch
	C-3. Report information regarding cooling system performance	Level 2: Automatic switching – 20 % Level 2: 0–9 % of parking spaces has recharging points Level 0: Not present (uncontrolled charging)
Ventilation	V-1a. Supply air flow control at the room level	Level 1: Runtime setting of heating and cooling plants following a predefined time schedule Level 1: With central indication of detected faults and alarms for at least two relevant TBS
Lighting	L-1a. Occupancy control for indoor lighting	
	L-2. Control artificial lighting power based on daylight levels	
Electric vehicle charging	EV-15. EV Charging Capacity	
	EV-16. EV Charging Grid balancing	
Monitoring & control	MC-3. Run time management of HVAC systems	
	MC-4. Detecting faults of technical building systems and providing support to the diagnosis of these faults	

Table 4Assigned weights to the technical domains of each impact criterion used for the case study ($w_{d,ic}$).

Technical domain	Impact criterion						
	Energy efficiency	Energy flexibility & storage	Comfort	Convenience	Health, well-being & accessibility	Maintenance & fault prediction	Information to occupants
Heating	0.302	0.417	0.16	0.1	0.16	0.359	0.114
Cooling	0.117	0.162	0.16	0.1	0.16	0.14	0.114
Domestic hot water	0.107	0.148	0	0.1	0	0.128	0.114
Ventilation	0.088	0	0.16	0.1	0.16	0.104	0.114
Lighting	0.12	0	0.16	0.1	0.16	0	0
Electricity	0.016	0.022	0	0.1	0	0.019	0.114
Dynamic building envelope	0.05	0	0.16	0.1	0.16	0.05	0.114
Electric vehicle charging	0	0.05	0	0.1	0	0	0.114
Monitoring & control	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2

Table 5Assigned weights to the impact criteria applying the equal weighting method (w_{ic}).

Energy efficiency	Energy flexibility & storage	Comfort	Convenience	Health, well-being & accessibility	Maintenance & fault prediction	Information to occupants
0.16667	0.33333	0.08333	0.08333	0.08333	0.16667	0.08333

Table 6Assigned weights to the impact criteria in relation to their key functionality applying the equal weighting method ($w_{f,ic}$).

Energy efficiency	Energy flexibility & storage	Comfort	Convenience	Health, well-being & accessibility	Maintenance & fault prediction	Information to occupants
0.5	1	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.5	0.25

Table 7Assigned weights to the key functionalities applying the equal weighting method (w_j).

Energy performance & operation	Response to the needs of occupants	Energy flexibility
0.33333	0.33333	0.33333

identifying details and the aggregation of data where necessary. Furthermore, data handling protocols were aligned with ethical standards and best practices for privacy protection, ensuring that the use of the SRI assessment results remained compliant with legal and regulatory requirements.

Before proceeding with the further analysis of the case study, it is essential to explain how the weightings for the main elements of the DSF methodology (described in Section 3.2) were specified for this example.

First, the weighting value of the technical domains for each impact criterion, used in Eq. (5), were assigned based on the predefined table proposed by the official SRI methodology [7] which takes into consideration the categorization of the building (climate zone and building type). For the given characteristics of the case building (South Europe, non-residential), this table is structured as follows (Table 4).

Regarding the impact criteria weights of Eq. (6), the equal weighting method was utilized, and the respective values are given in Table 5.

Similarly, the weighting of each impact criterion in relation to its key functionality, needed in Eq. (7), is also attributed via equal weighting, as shown in Table 6.

Lastly, Table 7 presents the weighting value of the key functionalities, which is again extracted through the equal weighting process and utilized in Eq. (8).

To ensure the scientific integrity of the IT identification process, an extensive literature review was conducted in the context of the specific case study, synthesizing data from existing research works [29] and projects [45]. This was complemented by comprehensive market research focused on both leading European technology providers (e.g., Siemens, ABB, Schneider Electric, Somfy) and international corporations with active operations within the EU market (e.g., Google, Honeywell, LG, Panasonic, Trina Solar). This dual approach ensures that the technological solutions considered are not only innovative but also affordable and widely accessible.

The extracted solutions (ITs) that formed the baseline for the determination of the scenarios proposed for the case study building upgrade, are displayed in Table 8. The table consists of the main IT, along with its related accessories, if any, the code of the smart ready services upgraded, the respective functionality level that each smart ready service achieves, and the total cost (including average purchase and installation cost).

5. Results

This section presents the results extracted from the case study. The first step is to calculate the current SRI score of the examined building. Based on the SRI calculation methodology described in Section 3 and the characteristics and applicable smart ready services of the case study building, the SRI assessment tool calculates the building's total SRI score at 15.2 %.

Then, a target SRI score needs to be defined as input to the DSF. For the purpose of this case study, the SRI goal was set at 30 %, so the tool can provide multiple upgrade solutions. Table 9 presents the list of the proposed upgrade scenarios and IT combinations derived from the DSF that satisfy the target SRI score, ranked by their cost effectiveness. Respectively, Table 10 shows the results based on the total investment cost, while Table 11 exhibits the outcomes, using the total SRI gain as

Table 8

Description of the intervention technologies that form the proposed scenarios for the case study.

Intervention technology	Smart ready service	Functionality Level	Smart ready service	Functionality Level	Total cost (€)
Google Nest Learning Thermostat (one room)	H-1a	Level 1	C-4	Level 2	377 €
	H-3	Level 2	DHW-1b	Level 1	
	H-4	Level 3	E-12	Level 4	
	C-1a	Level 1	MC-9	Level 1	
	C-3	Level 2			
Honeywell T9 Smart Thermostat (one room)	H-1a	Level 1	C-3	Level 2	321 €
	H-3	Level 1	C-4	Level 2	
	H-4	Level 2	MC-4	Level 1	
	C-1a	Level 1	MC-9	Level 1	
	C-3	Level 2			
Ecobee SmartThermostat (one room)	H-1a	Level 1	MC-4	Level 2	394 €
	H-2a	Level 2	MC-9	Level 2	
	C-1a	Level 1	MC-13	Level 3	
	V-1a	Level 3	MC-25	Level 2	
	E-12	Level 4	MC-29	Level 2	
	MC-3	Level 3	MC-30	Level 3	
Ecobee SmartThermostat (multiple rooms)	H-1a	Level 4	MC-4	Level 2	1970 €
	H-2a	Level 2	MC-9	Level 2	
	C-1a	Level 4	MC-13	Level 3	
	V-1a	Level 3	MC-25	Level 2	
	E-12	Level 4	MC-29	Level 2	
	MC-3	Level 3	MC-30	Level 3	
Danfoss ECL Comfort	H-1b	Level 2	DHW-1b	Level 1	1359 €
	H-1c	Level 1	C-1b	Level 2	
	H-1d	Level 3	C-1c	Level 2	
	H-2a	Level 1	C-1d	Level 3	
	H-2d	Level 3	C-1g	Level 1	
	DHW-1a	Level 1	C-2a	Level 3	
Bosch Compress 7000i AW	H-1b	Level 3	DHW-1b	Level 2	9109 €
	H-1c	Level 2	C-2a	Level 3	
	H-2b	Level 3	C-2b	Level 3	
	H-2d	Level 2	C-3	Level 4	
	H-4	Level 3	C-4	Level 3	
Grundfos MAGNA3	H-1d	Level 4	DHW-1a	Level 1	1051 €
	H-2a	Level 1	DHW-1b	Level 1	
	H-3	Level 1	C-1d	Level 4	
Siemens RVD250-A district heating controller Accessories: QAD22 strap-on sensor, QAE2120.010 immersion temperature sensor, QAP21.2 cable temperature sensor, QAC22 outside sensor, QBE2003-P16 pressure sensor, AP 257/51 weather station	H-1c	Level 2	DHW-1d	Level 3	3677 €
	DHW-1a	Level 3	MC-4	Level 3	
	DHW-1b	Level 3			
Schneider Electric Clipsal C-Bus Accessories: C-Bus Network Interface, C-Bus 8-Channel Dimmer, C-Bus Saturn Series Wall Series, C-Bus Multi Sensor	L-1a	Level 3	MC-9	Level 1	5450 €
	L-2	Level 4	MC-30	Level 2	
	DE-2	Level 3			
	E-3	Level 1			
Kostal Wallbox EV charger	EV-15	Level 4, if the examined building is a single-family residential building Level 3, if the examined building is a small multi-family residential building Level 2, if the examined building is a large multi-family residential building or non-residential building			2150 €
	EV-16	Level 1			
Siemens RMU710B-1 Universal controller Accessories: BAU200 Universal digital indicator, RMZ792 Bus operator unit, RMZ785 Universal module (8UD), OCI700.1 Service tool for KNX / LPB, OZW772.16 Web server for 16 Synco devices, GDB181.1E/BA VAV compact controller BACnet, SSA31.04 Electromotoric actuator	EV-17	Level 2			8721 €
	H-1c	Level 2	DHW-2b	Level 4	
	H-2d	Level 4	V-1a	Level 4	
	C-1c	Level 2	V-1c	Level 3	
	C-2a	Level 2	V-2c	Level 2	
	C-2b	Level 4	V-2d	Level 3	
Siemens UH50-A74-00 Ultrasonic heat meter Accessories: WZM-F270 Spacer DN 50, WZU-RF Radio module, WZU5-2815 Pair of temperature sensors Pt500	H-3	Level 4	DHW-3	Level 4	5436 €
	C-3	Level 4			
Siemens UP258D51 Presence Detector WIDE Accessories: UP258D51 Presence Detector, S 255/11 IR remote control	H-1a	Level 3	L-2	Level 4	4845 €
	C-1a	Level 3	V-6	Level 1	
	L-1a	Level 4			

Table 9

List of the proposed upgrade scenarios for the case study ranked by their cost effectiveness.

Upgrade scenario	Intervention technology	Final SRI score (%)	Cost effectiveness (€/SRI gain)
Scenario 1	Ecobee SmartThermostat (one room) Danfoss ECL Comfort	31.26	109.12
Scenario 2	Ecobee SmartThermostat (one room) Danfoss ECL Comfort	31.57	126.73
Scenario 3	Honeywell T9 Smart Thermostat (one room) Ecobee SmartThermostat (multiple rooms)	30.23	131.05
Scenario 4	Ecobee SmartThermostat (multiple rooms) Honeywell T9 Smart Thermostat (one room)	30.53	149.41
Scenario 5	Ecobee SmartThermostat (multiple rooms) Google Nest Learning Thermostat (one room) Siemens RVD250-A district heating controller	30.83	150.13

Table 10

List of the proposed upgrade scenarios for the case study ranked by their total cost.

Upgrade scenario	Intervention technology	Final SRI score (%)	Total cost (€)
Scenario 1	Ecobee SmartThermostat (one room) Danfoss ECL Comfort	31.26	1753
Scenario 3	Ecobee SmartThermostat (multiple rooms)	30.23	1970
Scenario 2	Ecobee SmartThermostat (one room) Danfoss ECL Comfort Honeywell T9 Smart Thermostat (one room)	31.57	2074
Scenario 4	Ecobee SmartThermostat (multiple rooms) Honeywell T9 Smart Thermostat (one room)	30.53	2291
Scenario 5	Ecobee SmartThermostat (multiple rooms) Google Nest Learning Thermostat (one room)	30.83	2347

the criterion. For each rank criterion, the five most efficient scenarios are presented. Furthermore, Figs. 2-4 include the same results in the form of charts.

As extracted from the results above, the recommended upgrade scenarios in each ranking metric are not necessarily identical or ranked in the same places. As expected, all five best solutions based on the cost effectiveness and the total cost are identical, as both metrics are cost oriented. Scenario 1 (Ecobee SmartThermostat (one room), Danfoss ECL Comfort) is set as the best solution in both methods, providing the lowest cost effectiveness (109.12 €/SRI gain) and the least total cost (1753 €). Nevertheless, some scenarios are ranked differently (scenarios 2 and 3 have switched positions in the two methods). The rest of the solutions in the two lists are also the same (scenarios 4 and 5). Regarding the SRI-based classification, the proposed solutions are naturally entirely different. In this case, the highest SRI gain (36.01 %) is extracted from scenario 6 (Ecobee SmartThermostat (multiple rooms), Schneider Electric Clipsal C-Bus, Siemens RVD250-A district heating controller,

Siemens RMU710B-1 Universal controller, Siemens UH50-A74-00 Ultrasonic heat meter). This highlights the importance of optimization criteria in selecting the optimal technological solution for a building's smartness upgrade.

The following Figs. 5-7 show the change in the values of the impact criteria, technical domains and key functionalities, respectively, from the initial state to scenario 1, which is the recommended one for minimizing the cost effectiveness and the total cost.

Regarding impact criteria, *Health, well-being, & accessibility* (from 24.75 % to 49.75 %), *Comfort* (from 19.64 % to 51.17 %), and *Energy efficiency* (from 29.41 % to 51.98 %) are the criteria with the largest increase in this case. The domains with the biggest impact are *Domestic hot water* (from 0 % to 23.33 %), *Monitoring & control* (from 14.07 % to 32.8 %), and *Ventilation* (from 9.38 % to 47.92 %), while the *Energy flexibility* key functionality has undergone the most significant increase, from 5.14 % to 18.31 %. Regarding the other key functionalities, *Energy performance & operation* has experienced a rise from 22.21 % to 35.64 %,

Table 11

List of the proposed upgrade scenarios for the case study ranked by the total SRI gain.

Upgrade scenario	Intervention technology	Final SRI score (%)	SRI gain (%)
Scenario 6	Ecobee SmartThermostat (multiple rooms) Schneider Electric Clipsal C-Bus Siemens RVD250-A district heating controller	Siemens RMU710B-1 Universal controller Siemens UH50-A74-00 Ultrasonic heat meter	51.21 36.01
Scenario 7	Ecobee SmartThermostat (multiple rooms) Schneider Electric Clipsal C-Bus Siemens RVD250-A district heating controller	Grundfos MAGNA3 Bosch Compress 7000i AW Siemens UH50-A74-00 Ultrasonic heat meter	51.20 36
Scenario 8	Ecobee SmartThermostat (multiple rooms) Schneider Electric Clipsal C-Bus Siemens RVD250-A district heating controller	Bosch Compress 7000i AW Siemens UH50-A74-00 Ultrasonic heat meter	51.20 36
Scenario 9	Ecobee SmartThermostat (multiple rooms) Siemens RVD250-A district heating controller Danfoss ECL Comfort	Kostal Wallbox EV charger Siemens UH50-A74-00 Ultrasonic heat meter Siemens RMU710B-1 Universal controller	51.19 35.99
Scenario 10	Ecobee SmartThermostat (one room) Siemens UP258D51 Presence Detector WIDE Siemens RVD250-A district heating controller	Siemens UH50-A74-00 Ultrasonic heat meter Danfoss ECL Comfort Siemens RMU710B-1 Universal controller	50.93 35.73

Fig. 2. Graphic presentation of the proposed upgrade scenarios for the case study ranked by their cost effectiveness.

Fig. 3. Graphic presentation of the proposed upgrade scenarios for the case study ranked by their total cost.

while *Responds to the need of occupants* from 18.15 % to 38.22 %.

Similarly, Figs. 8-10 illustrate the effects of the best upgrade scenario according to the total SRI gain; scenario 6.

First, it is clear that the impact criteria with the highest increase in scenario 6 are the same as the ones in scenario 1, namely *Health, well-being, & accessibility* (from 24.75 % to 73 %), *Comfort* (from 19.64 % to 70.63 %), and *Energy efficiency* (from 29.41 % to 73.37 %). Accordingly, *Lighting* (from 5.6 % to 92.8 %), *Ventilation* (from 9.38 % to 56.25 %), and *Domestic hot water* (from 0 % to 60 %) are the domains that received the greatest influence. *Cooling* has also reached a high percentage of 66.2 %, as indicated in the domain bar chart. Finally, *Energy flexibility* has seen the largest percentage increase, moving from 5.14 % to 27.29 %, however *Energy performance & operation* (from 22.21 % to 61.86 %) and *Responds to the need of occupants* (from 18.15 % to 58.39 %) have also gained notable increase.

6. Discussion

This study highlights the transformative potential of integrating the SRI into building evaluation and upgrade processes, significantly improving energy performance, user needs, and grid flexibility in buildings. It demonstrates how the SRI serves as a structured framework for bridging energy performance goals with practical strategies, aiding building owners in identifying cost-effective improvements via personalized upgrade recommendations. The case study shows SRI's adaptability to diverse building types and climates, positioning it as a versatile tool for sustainable urban development across the EU. The results are consistent with earlier studies which have identified the specific gaps and challenges related to the SRI's application. These challenges are related to the applicability of the SRI across various building types, climates, and regions, while converging on the need of incorporating the economic-related dimension into the framework. These findings formed

Fig. 4. Graphic presentation of the proposed upgrade scenarios for the case study ranked by their total SRI gain.

Fig. 5. Benefit at impact level from initial state to upgrade scenario 1.

the foundation for the introduction of the proposed decision-making framework. However, achieving the full potential of the SRI demands a detailed understanding of regional energy requirements, occupant behavior, and the technological maturity of available solutions. A key contribution of this research is the incorporation of individualized market-based solutions for commercial products and systems. By quantifying upgrade costs and their impact on SRI scores, the study offers stakeholders a practical, cost-effective approach. The decision support tool further simplifies this process by ranking interventions based on investment cost, SRI gain, and cost effectiveness. However, high initial costs, especially for older buildings or regions with limited access to affordable smart technologies, remain a challenge. Thus, the framework should be aligned with national subsidy schemes and EU incentives to improve affordability. For example, there are several funding schemes focused on energy efficiency, and one consideration is

that part of these funds could be leveraged to support the implementation of the SRI framework. The application of the DSF to a non-residential office building in Athens is presented for functionality testing, demonstration, and ease of application. However, several buildings of different typologies (such as residential, office, and educational) and located in various climate zones across Europe (including pilot cases from Spain, Czechia, Austria, Croatia, Latvia, Bulgaria, Romania, and Greece) have been thoroughly analyzed using this framework within the context of SRI-ENACT, an EU’s LIFE project (Grant agreement No. 101077201) that intends to engage partners at the national and EU levels to jointly develop services and tools for SRI adoption.

In addition, future versions of the SRI methodology and, subsequently, the proposed DSF could explore the integration of utility rates. Including dynamic pricing would enhance the economic analysis,

Fig. 6. Benefit at technical domain level from initial state to upgrade scenario 1.

Fig. 7. Benefit at key functionality level from initial state to upgrade scenario 1.

providing valuable insights into the cost effectiveness of smart technology adoption and improving investment decision-making, thereby increasing the real-world applicability of the SRI framework.

Regarding the SRI implementation, the overall procedure faces hurdles such as subjective assessments, inconsistent weighting factors, limited real-time data availability, and GDPR issues. These challenges can be mitigated by embedding the framework into standardized digital tools that apply predefined evaluation logic, structured input fields, and guided parameter selection. This approach not only reduces subjectivity and ensures consistency across assessors but also enhances usability by supporting non-expert users. Incorporating sensitivity analysis features enables users to explore how input variations affect outcomes, further reinforcing the robustness and interpretability of the results.

Additionally, the SRI evaluation process encounters gaps in addressing regional and climatic variations, which call for further customization of the methodology. For instance, given its sensitivity to

input parameters such as functionality scores and domain weightings, these elements should be customized based on local climatic and regulatory conditions, rendering the framework fully adaptable to individual cases. Such a customization of the weighting factors per climate zone for residential buildings was carried for the case of Greece [37]. Replicating such an approach across other countries and contexts could significantly enhance the relevance and effectiveness of SRI assessments. The findings of this study align with the 2024 EPBD amendments, which emphasize building digitalization and Nearly Zero Energy Buildings (nZEBs) promotion, offering a pathway to the EU’s 2050 climate neutrality goals. Future research should address these limitations, prioritize dynamic, real-time assessments enabled by advanced Method C tools, and explore synergies between the SRI and metrics like energy savings and occupant satisfaction.

Fig. 8. Benefit at impact level from initial state to upgrade scenario 6.

Fig. 9. Benefit at technical domain level from initial state to upgrade scenario 6.

Fig. 10. Benefit at key functionality level from initial state to upgrade scenario 6.

7. Conclusions

This study highlights the decisive role of the SRI in advancing the energy efficiency and sustainability of buildings across the EU, as it systematically evaluates and guides the integration of intelligent technologies that optimize energy use, comfort, and operational performance. Through a comprehensive case study of a non-residential office building in Athens, Greece, the research demonstrated that the SRI serves as an effective framework for evaluating building smartness, enabling the identification of targeted upgrades that enhance both smart readiness and energy performance. These upgrades, incorporating smart technologies such as advanced thermostats, heat pumps, and energy monitoring systems, showcased the feasibility of achieving significant improvements in energy efficiency and user comfort, while addressing financial constraints.

The integration of economic analysis into the SRI assessment framework further strengthened the research's practical value, aligning it more closely with the latest revisions of the EU's EPBD. The DSF identified cost-effective upgrade scenarios, as well as market-driven solutions, supporting informed decision-making for building owners and managers committed to achieving the EU's 2050 climate neutrality targets. However, although the proposed framework has been developed to be as inclusive as possible, its accuracy is interlinked to the input data used. That being said, several assumptions have been made. To begin with, the methodology relies on specific commercial technologies identified through market research. However, this list is not exhaustive, as numerous alternatives are available that could also contribute to smart readiness improvements. Additionally, the purchase and installation costs of the selected commercial technologies are estimations, which may vary significantly across EU countries due to factors such as local market conditions, labor costs, and taxation. Another key assumption concerns the maximum functionality level assigned to each technology, which has been estimated based on its technical specifications. This estimation introduces potential subjectivity and bias, as different interpretations of technology capabilities could yield varying SRI scores. Addressing these limitations in future research by expanding the technology database, incorporating real-world cost data, and refining functionality level assessments through expert validation would enhance the robustness and applicability of the proposed framework.

One of the key challenges identified is the high upfront cost associated with the implementation of smart technologies, which can act as a barrier for widespread adoption, particularly in buildings with limited renovation budgets. In addition, the study presented the results from the

framework's application on a single case study in Athens, limiting the generalizability of the findings across other geographic contexts. Future research should focus on validating the proposed DSF across a wider range of building types and geographic locations, possibly comparing the findings from the SRI-ENACT LIFE project (Grant agreement No. 101077201), which applied the framework in various EU countries and building types. This would help assess the adaptability and robustness of the methodology in diverse real-world contexts. Moreover, integrating AI-driven decision-making tools could enhance the personalization of upgrade recommendations and better capture user-specific needs. Long-term cost-benefit analyses of smart readiness upgrades are also recommended to support sustainable and affordable investment planning. Finally, standardizing SRI assessment methodologies will help ensure consistency across regions and building typologies.

Despite the underlying limitations, the implementation of SRI-driven upgrades at the building level carries significant policy implications that extend beyond individual structures to broader urban and economic benefits. Increasing a building's SRI score enhances its market value, as buildings with higher smart readiness are more attractive to buyers, tenants, and investors seeking energy-efficient and technologically advanced properties. Moreover, promoting SRI upgrades is essential for the development of smart cities, nZEBs and climate-resilient infrastructure, aligning with EU sustainability goals and digital transformation strategies. Additionally, the demand for smart building technologies creates new employment opportunities across multiple sectors, including construction, energy management, technology development, and building assessment, driving economic growth. Furthermore, by targeting key impact criteria such as health, well-being, comfort, and convenience, SRI upgrades contribute directly to improving occupant quality of life, making buildings more adaptive to user needs while enhancing their energy performance. These policy implications underscore the necessity for regulatory incentives and financial support mechanisms, such as subsidies, tax breaks, and awareness campaigns, to accelerate the widespread adoption of SRI-based smart building upgrades across the EU. In summary, this research emphasizes the importance of integrating smart readiness into national and the EU's energy and climate strategies, serving as a key metric for evaluating building performance, supporting regulatory compliance, and guiding policy development toward smart and sustainable infrastructure. To effectively assess the broader impact of SRI-related upgrades using the proposed framework, widespread adoption is necessary, with horizontal implementation at both national and potentially European levels. This paper demonstrates the functionality

of the framework and, through quantitative results at the building level, lays the groundwork for realizing the broader benefits aligned with national and EU targets.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Alexandros Xenakis: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Formal analysis. **Apostolos Arsenopoulos:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Ioannis Papias:** Writing – review & editing, Software, Data curation. **Filippos Serepas:** Writing – review & editing, Software, Data curation. **Stamatia Rizou:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **John Psararas:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

Alexandros Xenakis reports financial support was provided by European Commission. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- Climate action and the Green Deal, (n.d.). https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal/climate-action-and-green-deal_en (accessed January 31, 2025).
- European Court of Auditors, Special Report Energy efficiency in buildings: greater focus on cost-effectiveness still needed, 2020. https://www.eca.europa.eu/en/publications/SR20_11 (accessed March 7, 2025).
- F. Filippidou, J. Navarro, F. Filippidou, J. Pablo, Achieving the cost-effective energy transformation of Europe's buildings energy renovations via combinations of insulation and heating & cooling technologies methods and data, in: n.d. <https://doi.org/10.2760/278207>.
- A Guidebook to European Buildings Efficiency: Key regulatory and policy developments Report on the evolution of the European regulatory framework for buildings efficiency, (n.d.). <https://epb.center/epb-standards/energy-performance-buildings-directive-epbd/> (accessed January 31, 2025).
- N. Attoue, I. Shahrour, R. Younes, Smart building: use of the artificial neural network approach for indoor temperature forecasting, *Energies* 2018, Vol. 11, Page 395 11 (2018) 395. <https://doi.org/10.3390/EN11020395>.
- A. Ghaffarianhoseini, D. Clements-Croome, U. Raahemifar, K. Tookey, Intelligent smart cities and buildings: a critical exposition and a way forward, *Intelligent Buildings International Journal* 10 (2018) 122–129, <https://doi.org/10.1080/17508975.2017.1394810>.
- S. Verbeke, D. Aerts, G. Reynders, Y. Ma, P. Waide, Final report on the technical support to the development of a smart readiness indicator for buildings, (2020). <https://doi.org/10.2833/41100>.
- Official Journal of the European Union, Directive (EU) 2018/844 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2018 amending Directive 2010/31/EU on the energy performance of buildings and Directive 2012/27/EU on energy efficiency, (2018). <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:32018L0844> (accessed September 20, 2024).
- Legislative Train Schedule - European Parliament, Revision of the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive In "A European Green Deal (2025). <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/legislative-train/package-fit-for-55/file-revision-of-the-energy-performance-of-buildings-directive>, accessed January 31, 2025.
- Official Journal of the European Union, Commission delegated regulation (EU) 2020/2155 of 14 October 2020 supplementing directive (EU) 2010/31/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council by establishing an optional common European Union scheme for rating the smart readiness of buildings, (2020). https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg_del/2020/2155/oj/eng (accessed September 20, 2024).
- Official Journal of the European Union, Commission implementing regulation (EU) 2020/2156 of 14 October 2020 detailing the technical modalities for the effective implementation of an optional common Union scheme for rating the smart readiness of buildings scheme for rating the smart readiness of buildings, 2020. https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg_impl/2020/2156/oj/eng (accessed March 7, 2025).
- SRI test phases, (n.d.). https://energy.ec.europa.eu/topics/energy-efficiency/energy-efficient-buildings/smart-readiness-indicator/sri-eu-countries_en (accessed February 1, 2025).
- SRI implementation tools, (n.d.). https://energy.ec.europa.eu/topics/energy-efficiency/energy-efficient-buildings/smart-readiness-indicator/implementation-tools_en (accessed April 25, 2025).
- O. Horák, K. Kabele, Testing of pilot buildings by the SRI method, *Vytapeni, Vetrani, Instalace* (2019) 331–334. https://dspace.cvut.cz/bitstream/handle/10467/86913/Horak_Kabele_Testing_of_Pilot_Buildings_by_the_SRI_Method_%282019%29_PUBV_337372.pdf (accessed January 24, 2025).
- E. Jahnunen, L. Pulkka, A. Säynäjoki, S. Junnila, Applicability of the smart readiness indicator for cold climate countries, *Buildings* 9 (2019), <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings9040102>.
- P.A. Fokaides, C. Panteli, A. Panayidou, How are the smart readiness indicators expected to affect the energy performance of buildings: first evidence and perspectives, *Sustainability* (Switzerland) 12 (2020) 1–12, <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12229496>.
- B. Ramezani, M.G. da Silva, N. Simões, Application of smart readiness indicator for Mediterranean buildings in retrofitting actions, *Energy Build* (2021) 249, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2021.111173>.
- A.A. Volkov, E.I. Batov, Simulation of building operations for calculating building intelligence quotient, in: *Procedia Eng*, Elsevier Ltd, 2015: pp. 845–848. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proeng.2015.07.156>.
- E. Jahnunen, L. Leskinen, S. Junnila, The economic viability of a progressive smart building system with power storage, *Sustainability* (Switzerland) (2020) 12, <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12155998>.
- E. Markoska, N. Jakica, S. Lazarova-Molnar, M.K. Kragh, Assessment of building intelligence requirements for real time performance testing in smart buildings, 2019 4th International Conference on Smart and Sustainable Technologies, SpliTech 2019 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.23919/SPLITECH.2019.8783002>.
- J. Al Dakheel, C. Del Pero, N. Aste, F. Leonforte, Smart buildings features and key performance indicators: a review, *Sustain Cities Soc* (2020) 61, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2020.102328>.
- I. Vigna, R. Perneti, G. Pernigotto, A. Gasparella, Analysis of the building smart readiness indicator calculation: a comparative case-study with two panels of experts, *Energies* (Basel) (2020) 13, <https://doi.org/10.3390/en13112796>.
- T. Märzinger, D. Österreicher, extending the application of the smart readiness indicator a methodology for the quantitative assessment of the load shifting potential of smart districts, *Energies* (Basel) (2020) 13, <https://doi.org/10.3390/en13133507>.
- C. Becchio, S.P. Corgnati, G. Crespi, M.C. Pinto, S. Viazzo, Exploitation of dynamic simulation to investigate the effectiveness of the Smart Readiness Indicator: application to the Energy Center building of Turin, *Sci Technol Built Environ* 27 (2021) 1127–1143, <https://doi.org/10.1080/23744731.2021.1947657>.
- I. Martínez, B. Zalba, R. Trillo-Lado, T. Blanco, D. Cambra, R. Casas, Internet of things (IoT) as sustainable development goals (sdg) enabling technology towards smart readiness indicators (sri) for university buildings, *Sustainability* (Switzerland) (2021) 13, <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13147647>.
- L. Canale, M. De Monaco, B. Di Pietra, G. Puglisi, G. Ficco, I. Bertini, M. Dell'isola, Estimating the smart readiness indicator in the Italian residential building stock in different scenarios, *Energies* (Basel) (2021) 14, <https://doi.org/10.3390/en14206442>.
- V. Apostolopoulos, P. Giourka, G. Martinopoulos, K. Angelakoglou, K. Kourtzanidis, N. Nikolopoulos, Smart readiness indicator evaluation and cost estimation of smart retrofitting scenarios - A comparative case-study in European residential buildings, *Sustain Cities Soc* 82 (2022), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2022.103921>.
- G. Plienaitis, M. Daukšys, E. Demetriou, B. Ioannou, P.A. Fokaides, L. Seduikyte, Evaluation of the smart readiness indicator for educational buildings, *Buildings* 13 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings13040888>.
- I.A. Campodonico Avendano, K. Heimar Andersen, S. Erba, A. Moazami, M. Aghaei, B. Najafi, A novel framework for assessing the smartness and the smart readiness level in highly electrified non-residential buildings: a Norwegian case study, *Energy Build* (2024) 314, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2024.114234>.

- [30] A.N. Tak, B. Becerik-Gerber, L. Soibelman, G. Lucas, A framework for investigating the acceptance of smart home technologies: findings for residential smart HVAC systems, *Build Environ* 245 (2023), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2023.110935>.
- [31] Y. Li, S. Kubicki, A. Guerriero, Y. Rezgui, Review of building energy performance certification schemes towards future improvement, *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 113 (2019), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2019.109244>.
- [32] T. Märzinger, D. Österreicher, Supporting the smart readiness indicator-A methodology to integrate a quantitative assessment of the load shifting potential of smart buildings, *Energies (Basel)* (2019) 12, <https://doi.org/10.3390/en12101955>.
- [33] S. Koltisios, P. Fokaidis, P.Z. Georgali, A.C. Tsolakis, P. Chatzipanagiotidou, E. Klumbytė, A. Jurelionis, L. Seduikytė, C. Kontopoulos, C. Malavazos, C. Panteli, M. Sušnik, G. Cebirat, D. Ioannidis, D. Tzovaras, An enhanced framework for next-generation operational buildings energy performance certificates, *Int J Energy Res* 46 (2022) 20079–20095, <https://doi.org/10.1002/er.8517>.
- [34] L. Seduikyte, P.-Z. Morsink-Georgali, C. Panteli, P. Chatzipanagiotidou, K. Stavros, L. Stasiulienė, P. Spūdys, D. Pupeikis, A. Jurelionis, P. Fokaidis, Next-generation energy Performance certificates, what novel implementation do we need?, (n.d.). <https://doi.org/10.34641/clima.2022.348>.
- [35] C. Bleil de Souza, A. Badyina, O. Golubchikov, OntoAgency: an agency-based ontology for tracing control, ownership and decision-making in smart buildings, *Build Environ* 256 (2024), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2024.111489>.
- [36] P. Samaras, E. Stamatopoulos, A. Arsenopoulos, E. Sarmas, E. Marinakis, Readiness to adopt the smart Readiness indicator scheme across Europe: a multi-criteria decision analysis approach, in: 2024 IEEE International Workshop on Metrology for Living Environment, *MetroLivEnv 2024 - Proceedings*, Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers Inc., 2024, pp. 268–273, <https://doi.org/10.1109/MetroLivEnv60384.2024.10615377>.
- [37] A. Arsenopoulos, E. Stamatopoulos, P. Samaras, G. Xexakis, J. Psarras, Spotlighting the significance of the SRI methodological tailoring at country level: a case study in Greece, in: 15th International Conference on Information, Intelligence, Systems and Applications, *IISA 2024*, Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers Inc., 2024, <https://doi.org/10.1109/IISA62523.2024.10786716>.
- [38] I. Qaisar, W. Liang, K. Sun, T. Xing, Q. Zhao, An experimental comparative study of energy saving based on occupancy-centric control in smart buildings, *Build Environ* 268 (2025) 112322, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2024.112322>.
- [39] P. Oluwagbemiga Abgoola, U.O. Nnezi, Exploring the symbiotic relationship between smart technologies and thermal comfort in urban environments, *Social Sciences and Humanities Open* 10 (2024), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssaoh.2024.100943>.
- [40] P. Michailidis, P. Pelitaris, C. Korkas, I. Michailidis, S. Baldi, E. Kosmatopoulos, Enabling optimal energy management with minimal iot requirements: a legacy a/c case study, *Energies (Basel)* (2021) 14, <https://doi.org/10.3390/en14237910>.
- [41] P. Danassis, K. Siozios, C. Korkas, D. Soudris, E. Kosmatopoulos, A low-complexity control mechanism targeting smart thermostats, *Energy Build* 139 (2017) 340–350, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2017.01.013>.
- [42] C.D. Korkas, S. Baldi, I. Michailidis, E.B. Kosmatopoulos, Intelligent energy and thermal comfort management in grid-connected microgrids with heterogeneous occupancy schedule, *Appl Energy* 149 (2015) 194–203, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2015.01.145>.
- [43] C.D. Korkas, S. Baldi, I. Michailidis, E.B. Kosmatopoulos, Occupancy-based demand response and thermal comfort optimization in microgrids with renewable energy sources and energy storage, *Appl Energy* 163 (2016) 93–104, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2015.10.140>.
- [44] SRI-ENACT | Home, (n.d.). <https://srienact.eu/> (accessed January 24, 2025).
- [45] easySRI | Home, (n.d.). <https://www.easysri.eu/en> (accessed September 20, 2024).
- [46] BuildON | Home, (n.d.). <https://buildon-project.eu/> (accessed January 24, 2025).